

The Effect Of Stress Play Exercises On Developing Physical And Skill Performance And Performance Effectiveness for Football Players Inside The Futsal Youth

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Abstract

The game of indoor football is characterized by physical and skill performance with high efforts throughout the competition period and this time interspersed with a changing physical effort from time to time according to the requirements and conditions of the game. They are the repercussions of poor physical performance that leads to a poor level of skill and effectiveness in players. Performance during the competition, which may lead to unsatisfactory results in the match, and this is only with exercises similar to those efforts, especially when using a training method similar to the movements of the players, which is playing pressure exercises that contribute to refining the physical and skill performance of the football players indoors because of their movements and personalities similar to m. Tactically during the competition, as well as characterized by physical skills and football performance inside the halls with high privacy with the fitness capabilities of many, especially the distinctive strength of speed, agility, speed of performance and other things that led the coaches to how the players reached the high specifications that qualify them to enter the competition with full force High, hence the study problem manifested in the effect of stressful playing exercises that most teams use as offensive and defensive. A weapon in the first moment when you lose the ball for its great importance in building the attack in all its forms, as well as the first defensive organization to extract the ball quickly and not give the opponent an opportunity to act on it, few have noticed the use of these exercises by most of our clubs by watching and following the matches of the Iraqi Football League during the half And our contribution to making them challenge the behavior of training personnel to know the role of these exercises in the success of physical performance, the skill and effectiveness of the players' performance, and then the success of the team.

Introduction

Training means and methods are among the most important elements of the success of the training process, which is the cornerstone of the physical, skill, tactical, functional and psychological construction of the players. This will only be achieved by continuing and searching for more advanced training methods that keep pace with the development of the game in all aspects, physical, skill and linear, in order to improve these aspects more. It is appropriate to the requirements of the game, and as the game of indoor football is characterized by physical and skill performance with high efforts throughout the competition period, and this time is interspersed with changing physical efforts from time to time according to the requirements and conditions of the match, which means that the players must be at a high level of different physical performances in order to The level of skillful and tactical performance is at its best in the players, and what are the repercussions of poor physical performance that leads to a weak skill level and effectiveness of the players' performance during the competition, which may lead to unsatisfactory results in the match, and this is only with exercises similar to those efforts, especially when using a training method similar to the movements Players, which are stressful playing exercises that contribute to refining those physical and skill performances of the player In futsal football because of its movements and activities similar to the tactical movements of the players during the competition, we note, for example, the progress of the team's players in the opponent's court and in front of his penalty area to pressure him to force him to lose the ball and exhaust him physically and skillfully, as well as knowing the role of these exercises in the effectiveness of the team's performance that may They are positive through the correct performance of the tactical moves, and hence the importance of the study lies in knowing the extent of the role of stressful playing exercises in developing the physical and skill performance and the effectiveness of performance of football players indoors, in addition to proving that these exercises will be consistent with the requirements of the game in all its aspects or not, through By highlighting it by using it on football players

indoors to make it a training that helps to develop physical, skill and planning abilities, as well as the physical and skill performance in futsal football is characterized by a high specificity because it is linked to many physical abilities, especially the strength that is distinguished by speed, agility, speed of performance and others, which prompted coaches to how Reaching players to high specifications that qualify them to enter the competition with high competence, and this ability with skills to It is only with special exercises for some of the tactical aspects related to the requirements of the game, which are characterized by the speed of implementation and speed of performance by the players. Or the difficulty of the players' performance to confuse the opponent's defenses and its various organizations, and thus the effectiveness of the offensive performance is weak for the players. On the contrary, in the defensive aspects, we notice the weakness of the physical level in the transitional speed and the return to taking defensive places, for example, when losing the ball or skill performance that is always accompanied by technical errors that cause confusion for the team, especially if the team faces a good competitor Direct pressure play against him in his stadium, and from here the problem of the study was manifested in the effect of stressful playing exercises that most teams use as an offensive and defensive weapon at the first moment when the ball is lost because of its great importance in building the attack in its forms, as well as the first defensive organization to extract the ball quickly and not give an opportunity For the competitor to act out, and the lack of use of this exercise by most of our clubs has been noticed by watching and when Several matches of the Iraqi Football League indoors and as a contribution from us to make them challenge the behavior of the training personnel to know the role of these exercises in the success of physical and skill performance and the effectiveness of performance of the players and then the success of the team.

The aim of the study

1. Preparing stress playing exercises for football players inside the futsal.
2. Identify the differences between the tests and tribal posteriori performance of physical and skill and effectiveness of a disease and the experimental and control groups.
3. Identify the differences between the tests posteriori performance of physical and skill and effectiveness of a between the experimental and control groups disease.

Study methodology and field procedures

The researcher used the pilot's approach to the validity of the study of the problem, and a deliberate sample was selected, they are the players of the Basra Youth Club in oil and oil south of football inside the showrooms and participate in the Iraqi youth league for the season 2020-2021 AD. (24) Players distributed the sample members into two groups and each group included 12 players, where homogeneity and equivalence were performed as shown in Table (1).

Table (1) shows the arithmetic averages, standard deviations, coefficient of variation and (t) value calculated for the variables (height - weight - age - training age) for the experimental and control groups.

Variables	experimental group			control group			Calculated (t) value	indication
	s	P	Variation coefficient	s	P	Variation coefficient		
Age	4 . 18	4 . 2	%13.04	18.5	8 . 1	%9.7	0.98	Non - legal entity
training age	4 . 4	3 . 1	%28	1 . 4	88 . 0	%4 . 21	83 . 0	Non - legal entity
Length	2 . 173	7 . 3	%1 . 2	2 . 175	9 . 4	%7 . 2	1 . 1	Non - legal entity
the weight	8 . 72	06 . 3	%2 . 4	3 . 71	3.01	%2 . 3	1.2	Non - legal entity

The value of (T) table (1.3) at the degree of freedom (22) and the level of significance (0.05)

Tests used:

1- Physical exams:

1. First: Performance Endurance Test - Skilled Performance Endurance Test (5:50).
2. Second: Measurement of the characteristic force of speed - the partridge test for the maximum distance (10) seconds (10: 154).
3. Third: Performance Speed Test - Wall Passing Test (7:254).
4. Fourth: The test of agility - the test of running zigzag between the legs in the form of (8) (139: 6).

2- Skill tests:

1. First: Pass the skill test: grab towards a small target at a distance of (10) meters (4:46).
2. Second: Dribbling test: running zigzag between five columns back and forth (2:36).
3. Third: Scoring test of stability: Scoring with a goal divided by degrees at a distance of (10 m) (12:83).

3- Equation for measuring the effectiveness of the defensive and offensive performance of the player in the matches:

- The success rate of the defensive performance of the player in matches = Total unsuccessful defensive performance of the player in the matches + (2 × Total successful defensive performance of the player) / Total unsuccessful defensive performance of the team in matches + (2 × Total successful defensive performance of the team) .

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This equation is used to measure the success rate of a player's defensive performance in matches, it is also used to measure the success rate of offensive performance, but it replaces the offensive performance of the player in place of the defensive performance (5:67).

Presentation and discussion of the results:

Presenting and discussing the results of the differences between physical and skill tests and the effectiveness of pre and post-performance:

Table (2) It shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations and (t) value calculated for physical performance tests, before and after, for the two experimental and control groups.

Indication	value (t) calculated	post test		Pretest		Alone measurement	physical abilities	the group
		p	s	p	S			
Moral	9.5	2.16	31.9	2.1	32.4	sec	Carrying only disease	Experimental
Moral	8 . 4	0.92	5 . 39	09 . 1	6 . 32	meter	speed power	
Moral	71 . 3	29 . 0	35 . 7	54 . 0	01 . 8	Number	The speed of a disease	
Moral	4 . 2	5 5 . 0	64 . 13	6 5 . 0	19 . 14	sec	agility	
Moral	7.4	2.03	32.3	1.9	33.7	sec	Carrying only disease	control
Moral	05 . 10	51 . 0	7 . 36	83 . 0	08 . 33	meter	speed power	
Moral	2.06	0.19	7.98	0.88	8.4	Number	The speed of a disease	
Moral	3.9	0.21	14.2	0.92	14.73	sec	agility	

The value of (T) table (1.7) at the degree of freedom (11) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through table (2) we find all values (t) calculated by the size of the tabular differences, and this appears significantly for the physical tests and for the post-test, and two experimental and control ones attributed to the researcher. This moral has the right and proper planning of the exercises used to define a special period and link it to the skill performance according to the appropriate training methods for it and which contributed to its development, and this is consistent with what was indicated by (Abu Al-Ela A. Hamad).) by saying: "Using the training load in the correct manner leads to the success of the training process and thus raise the level of performance and achieve good results" (1: 55) .

Table (3) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and (t) value of the performance tests before and after the skill for the experimental and control groups.

indication	Calculated) t (valu e	post test		frying test		measurin g unit	skills	the group
		P	S	p	s			
moral	8 . 16	.0 67	4 . 5	.0 44	2 . 3	Degree	the pass	Experimenta l
moral	17 . 4	.0 19	4 . 10	.0 36	.11 03	time	dribblin g	
moral	9 . 3	.0 56	2 . 7	.0 88	8 . 5	Degree	scoring	
moral	7 . 2	.0 42	1 . 4	.0 27	6 . 3	Degree	the pass	control
insignifican t	3 . 2	.0 17	.11 01	.0 31	8 . 11	time	dribblin g	
moral	23 . 4	.0 24	3 . 6	.0 65	2 . 5	Degree	scoring	

The value of (T) table (1.7) at the degree of freedom (11) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through table (3), we find a value (t) calculated for the skill of dribbling, the control group was a small tabular group, and this indicates a lack of Manuata, while the values of (v) the skill of passing and recording were tabular size, which means significant differences in favor of the post-test. Moral soccer players inside the showrooms are trained in small areas and many repetitions of motor skills and to a high extent during the daily training units, and this is what secures the exercises played by the compressor in particular, similar to the movements of playing, which contributed to better performance of the skill, and this refers to it (Abd Ali Nassif and Kassim Hassan Hussein) by saying: ((Exercises that used E. contained an element of the competency or sports game being an effective, important and effective means when related to the characteristics of physical and technical skills of the game)) (9: 87) .

Table (4)It shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the (t) value calculated to measure the effectiveness of performance for the pre- and post-test and for the experimental and control groups.

indication	value) t(calculated	post test		Pretest		Alone measurement	The effectiveness of a disease	the group
		p	s	p	S			
moral	4.1	3.3	8.12	2.3	5.62	Degree	successful defense	Experimental
moral	3.02	2.41	5.2	3.35	7.04	Degree	Failed defense	
moral	2.7	3.91	7.98	3.01	5.63	Degree	successful attack	
moral	3.9	2.5	4.06	4.04	6.78	Degree	failed attack	
Non - legal entity	1.6	2.3	5.75	3.09	6.38	Degree	successful defense	Of the officer
Non - legal entity	1.03	3.1	7.4	3.42	7.61	Degree	Failed defense	
moral	4.02	1.77	5.97	3.5	6.21	Degree	successful attack	
moral	5.1	2.9	6.3	2.6	7.1	Degree	failed attack	

The value of (T) table (1.7) at the degree of freedom (11) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through table (4), we find the calculated (t) values for the experimental group, as well as the effectiveness of the attack control group, which is the size of the scheduled value, which shows significant differences in favor of the post-test. Effective promotion of the performance of each player and, consequently, the team as a whole. The ability of the defensive and offensive performance of the players during the exercise and its application in a consistent manner with the playing plans as in the game, and this is confirmed by (Hanafi Mahmoud Mukhtar) by saying (the coach must be well aware of the rule that says he does not perform in the exercise does not perform in the game, no B means E Players have not practiced wall-passing tactics well in E. They are not satisfied with executing them in games (3:15) .

Presenting and discussing the results of the differences between the dimensions of tests for physical performance and the skill and effectiveness of Wireless E performance between the two groups:

Table (5)It shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the computed t-value for the post-test of physical performance between the two groups.

indication	Calculated (t) value	control group		experimental group		measuring unit	physical abilities
		p	S	p	s		
moral	7.2	2.03	32.3	2.16	31.9	sec	Carrying only disease
moral	7	51 , 0	7 . 36	93 . 0	5 . 39	meter	speed power
moral	2.8	0.19	7.98	29 . 0	35 . 7	sec	The speed of a disease
moral	4.4	0.21	14.2	55 . 0	64 . 13	sec	Agility

The value of (v) is tabulated (1.3) at the degree of freedom (22) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through table (5), it becomes clear to us the calculated t-values with a tabular size, which means statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group, and the researcher attributed the reason for this to the fact that this result is clear evidence of E.N. Exercises for stress play that use its effect directly in The physical performance of the players is not improved, as they play sports quietly and play-like movements and under direct pressure from the opponent, who generate fast movements such as agility and satisfactory speed only. In terms of only bearing the efforts of these pressing exercises accompanied by a satisfactory technical tactical and team performance, as we observe the players' movements in competition for defense and attack situations, and interspersed with playing plans that require high skill performance before. Players and a special ability to endurance and this is confirmed by (Mowafaq the Lord) he said ((The exercise compressor has a great fake training to return the player's performance skills with accuracy, maximum strength and speed to the disease

during a certain time, as playing (4 vs 2) in an area (25 m x 15 AD) This shows us the material burden on the players on Monday, which contributes to increasing the material level for them) (11:109) .

Table (6) shows the arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and the calculated (t) value for the post-test of skill performance between the two groups.

indication	Calculated) t (value	control group		experimental group		measuring unit	Skills
		P	s	p	s		
moral	4 . 4	42 . 0	1 . 4	67 . 0	4 . 5	Degree	the pass
moral	1.5	17 . 0	01 . 11	19 . 0	4 . 10	Time	dribbling
moral	6 . 5	24 . 0	3 . 6	56 . 0	2 . 7	Degree	Scoring

The value of (v) is tabulated (1.3) at the degree of freedom (22) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through table (6) we find all the values (t) calculated by the size of the tabular differences, which means that there is a significant difference between the two groups in favor of the experimental group. Skilled by the players to get rid of pressure or find an opportunity to score, as well as the large number of receiving the ball and moving it on the field, as well as to perform a skill and other individual skills without the ball (Calgary free - covering - attribution - deception) and these skills require high agility and speed of performance. Well in every attack or situation my players play and this is a continuous and similar drill to compete through a lot of these drills that contain a high disease skill always that will be an important result in D. Develop your performance skills, basic only, especially passing, dribbling and scoring, which is one of the basic skills in futsal in which the game will be under the pressure of the opponent throughout the duration of the match, and this is in line with the phrase (a favourite spondylitis) ((E. The general objective To pick a title from this exercise, the data for the E a counter period and before the competition are limited to E. Missing players and having them organize the course of the competition so you can win (E Li A on levels) (8:15) .

Table (7) shows circles, standard deviations, and (t) value calculated for the efficacy test of Meta-A between the two disease groups.

indication	Calculated v	control group		experimental group		measuring unit	performance efficacy
		p	S	p	S		
moral	2.4	2.3	5.75	3.3	8.12	Degree	successful defense
moral	1.5	3.1	7.4	2.41	5.2	Degree	Failed defense
moral	2.4	1.77	5.97	3.91	7.98	Degree	successful attack
moral	2.7	2.9	6.3	2.5	4.06	Degree	failed attack

The value of (v) is tabulated (1.3) at the degree of freedom (22) and the level of significance (0.05) .

Through Table No. (7) it becomes clear to us the calculated (t) values of the size of the tabular differences, and this shows statistically significant differences between the two groups in favor of the experimental group, as the researcher One On believes the reason for this The superiority in the effectiveness of the experimental group is the use of stress-play exercises and its effect is clear on the tactical and success of players with skill disease through defensive and offensive exercises as well as containment situations and movements. Similar to what happens in the game, which helps to raise the technical level of the players in all physical and skill aspects, and connect them tactically with one of them in general tactical situations in the game, and this is what we see from the exercises. Operating the compressor, which gives a great opportunity for the player to bear the burdens of the game and how quickly decisions are made with skill performance and then success on any performance tactic under direct pressure from the competitor, which means reducing the wrong skills only and tactically and this is what Char Leah (Zuhair Al-Khashab and other contributors) said by saying ((Increasing the effectiveness of The team cannot achieve this not by reducing the technical error committed by the players and the team, as well as increasing the player's movement in general, which will help raise the level of disease in the game and achieve the desired results" (6: 141) .

Conclusions

1. The exercises prepared with stressful play have a positive role in the development of physical performance, skills and performance effectiveness.
2. The study showed the speed of development of the football players inside the futsal schematically, because the exercises used in stressful play are in line with the requirements of the game schematically.
3. The experimental group was superior to the control group in the post tests of the study variables.
4. The lack of significant performance in the defensive cases of the control group, which indicates the weakness of the use of modernity in exercises by the training staff.

References

- Abu Al-Alaa. Hamad Abdel-Fattah: Sports training and health burden, Cairo, Arab Thought House, 1996.
- Ismail Salem Abd: Determining the most important physical and skill capabilities for selecting young football players, Master Thesis, College of Physical Education, University of Baghdad, 2002.
- Hanafi Mahmoud Mokhtar: Football Training at CES, Cairo, Arab Thought House, 2000.
- Rahim Attia Janani. Building an experimental battery to measure the physical and skill traits of young football players in Iraq. PhD thesis. College of Physical Education, University of Basra, 2002.
- Razak Hussein Odeh: The effect of compound exercises in developing speed and endurance of skill performance in futsal football, Master's thesis, Surra University, 2012.
- Zuhair al-Khashab and others: Football, Mosul, University Press, 1999.
- Taha Ismail and others: Football between theory and practice, physical preparation, Cairo, Arab Thought House, 1989.
- Zulfiqar Saleh Abdul Hussein: Preparing football players for competitions, Jordan, Dar Al-Rawaq, 2016.
- Abd Ali Nassif and Kassim Hassan Hussein: Principles of Sports Training, Baghdad, Higher Education Press, 1980.
- Abdullah HasanJabbar. et, al (2018), Chemical synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles induced biocompatibility for anticancer activity. Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development, 9 (11). pp, 352-357.
- Kassim Hassan Hussein and Bastawisi A. Hamad: Isotonic muscle training in the field of sports events, Baghdad, Al-Watan Al-Arabi Press, 1979.
- Muwafaq Al-Rabb: The Tactical Knife in Football, Baghdad, Higher Education Press, 1990.
- WisamKamal Shamal: The effect of physical on some special physical abilities, vital variables, and the level of performance of the scoring skill in the football quintet, Master's thesis, College of Physical Education, University of Baghdad, 2006.

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